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CONSUMER TRUST IN THE BRAND: ROLE AND IMPORTANCE IN BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

Consumer trust in a brand is a key factor for successful business in the modern world. Brand trust can be defined as the confidence consumers have that a brand will deliver on its promises and provide quality products or services.

Trust is formed based on the experience of interacting with the brand, reviews not only from other consumers, but from key stakeholders, as well as the company's reputation [1].

In an increasingly competitive environment, companies strive not only to attract new customers, but also to retain existing ones.

This work examines the main aspects of building consumer trust in a brand, its impact on customer loyalty and ways to strengthen the image. This is a socio-psychological phenomenon based on consumer belief in the reliability, quality and value of the brand provided.

According to the results [2], it is proven that trust is one of the key reasons why customers buy goods or services, how much they are ready to buy a product of this particular brand.

Trust builds loyalty and builds a good reputation. Trust is the basis of emotional connections with organizations. According to studies [3], the evaluation of reputation is 91% correlated with trust in the organization. Therefore, it can be concluded that trust is an invaluable asset in the relationship between a brand and a customer, significant for business development.

Consumer trust is influenced by many factors, which can be tentatively divided into several categories: product and service quality, business transparency and honesty, brand reputation, customer service, and social proof.

The quality of goods and services is a determining factor in the formation of trust in the company and the brand. Products must meet the stated characteristics and expectations of consumers, as high-quality products increase trust. In addition, compliance with standards and the presence of certificates are physical evidence that demonstrably confirm the quality of goods and services.

Consumers appreciate access to complete information about the product:

- composition,
- production process,
- origin of raw materials.

Companies that openly communicate about their activities and conduct business honestly deserve more trust.

Another factor related to honesty is transparent marketing communications, which help avoid misunderstanding and disappointment on the part of consumers.

Inflated expectations due to unfair advertising lead to disappointment and loss of customers.

Brand trust directly affects consumer loyalty.

Research shows that consumers who trust a brand are more likely to make repeat purchases and recommend the brand to others.

In addition, trust reduces the sensitivity of consumers to prices and negative reviews.

Companies that respond to feedback and criticism, constructively and promptly solve problems, quickly respond to consumer complaints, deserve more trust. This approach affects customer loyalty. Social media is a platform for brand promotion [4]. Creating an effective promotion strategy in social networks increases brand recognition.

The social responsibility of the business, the use of ESG principles, participation in social and environmental initiatives increases the level of trust in the brand.

Positive reviews and recommendations from other consumers create the effect of social proof, increasing trust.

High ratings on independent platforms and positive reviews from authoritative sources also contribute to the growth of trust.

The main strategies for strengthening trust in the brand are focused on 2 components of marketing activity:

- the product and its quality;
- the company's communication policy (quality of communications with clients and stakeholders; PR).

A strategy based on improving the quality of products and services implies constant improvement of the quality of products and services to meet the expectations and needs of consumers. Here is the company's client-oriented strategy.

A strategy based on communications involves transparent interaction between internal and external stakeholders. Open and honest communication with consumers, provision of complete and reliable information about the company's products, services and activities. Quick and effective response to consumer requests and complaints, provision of mechanisms for collecting and analyzing feedback. Active participation in social and environmental projects, demonstration of social responsibility and adherence to ethical standards contributes to the creation of a positive image of the company.

In the conditions of increased competition and availability of information, consumer trust in the brand becomes critically important for the sustainable development of the company.

Consumers are increasingly careful in their choices, giving preference to brands they trust.

Conducting research and analyzing data on consumer trust in the brand allows companies to understand their needs and expectations, as well as the effectiveness of applied strategies.

Regular monitoring makes it possible to identify changes in consumer preferences and respond promptly to them.

Thus, understanding the importance of consumer trust in the company's brand and applying appropriate strategies help not only retain existing customers, but also attract new ones, creating the basis for sustainable growth and development in the market. This is a fundamental element of successful business in the modern world. Understanding the mechanisms of ego formation, applying effective strategies for strengthening and constant brand development based on data analysis and research help companies create long-term and stable relationships with clients.

Reference:

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